

The Impact of Corporate Culture on Employee Innovation Behavior: A Study of Zhejiang Textile and Garment Enterprises

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Abstract

Based on the theoretical research of enterprise culture and employee innovation behavior, combined with the current situation and development trend of textile industry, the paper comprehensively considered the influencing factors of textile enterprise culture, conducted expert interviews, and constructed the measurement scale of textile and garment enterprise culture. Field research is conducted on textile and apparel enterprises in the strategic alliance of textile economy and business management innovation, and a large number of questionnaires are distributed, the influence of cultural characteristics of textile and apparel companies on employee innovation behavior is verified using multiple regression analysis. This paper summarizes the definition and measurement of enterprise culture, and constructs a measurement scale suitable for textile and garment enterprise culture by referring to the existing research results of relevant literature at home and abroad. This paper introduces the perspective of employee's work engagement and explores, promotes the research on the influence of textile and garment enterprise cultural characteristics on employee innovation behavior to a more in-depth stage, and demonstrates the research hypothesis through empirical analysis, thus providing basic information and data for further study in this field. Through empirical analysis of textile and garment enterprises, this paper verifies that the four dimensions of characteristics of textile and garment enterprise culture have a significant impact on employee innovation behavior under the influence of mediating variables of employees' work engagement. It provides practical data and theoretical significance for textile and garment enterprises in the construction of enterprise culture in the future, and provides strong theoretical support for textile and garment enterprises to maintain continuous innovation ability in the market competition environment.

Keywords: *Textile and garment enterprise, Cultural characteristics, Employee innovation behavior, Work engagement.*

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INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

As one of the pillar industries of China's national economy, textile and garment industry has been playing a pivotal role in the consumption, increase of employment rate, import and export of China's national economy for a long time. As one of the pillar industries of China's export trade, textile industry accounts for 25% of China's export volume. Since 1987, China's textile and garment export has always maintained the first position in the world, which shows that the position of textile and garment industry in China's sustainable development is difficult to replace in a short period of time. (Cheng 2021; Jia et al. 2020) Since China joined the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001, the textile and garment industry has entered the melting pot of global competition, which has brought new opportunities and challenges to China's textile and garment industry. With the globalization of the economy, the development of enterprises also began to focus on internationalization. Especially in developing countries, the system is not perfect, in the face of the increasingly complex international situation in the process, China's textile and apparel enterprises must master the market competitiveness in the road to international competition, in order to stand in an invincible position. However, it is outdated to only rely on the improvement of product quality and service level to enhance the core competitiveness. Especially under the new situation, the shortage of energy and the rising price of resources have become the arduous problems that textile and garment enterprises must face. Driven by this situation, only by continuous innovation and continuous improvement of competitive advantages can they seize the opportunity in the competition. Innovation as the fundamental driving force and continuous source to promote human development and progress has been paid attention to by enterprises and scholars since ancient times. The ultimate practitioner of innovation is the individual, who is the most precious resource in the enterprise and the initiator of all ideas. Only relying on the individual who master the innovation ability, can the textile and garment enterprises master the core competitiveness in the continuous innovation. Employees are the main body and implementer of innovation, and the successful implementation of employees' creative ideas at the organizational level is the foundation and source of enterprise innovation. However, according to relevant survey reports, the first factor hindering the development of enterprises is the lack of such innovative talents in enterprises (Cheng 2021; Jia et al. 2020). Previous studies have shown that scholars tend to focus their research on innovation at the organizational level, but little on the individual level of employee innovation behavior. According to the theoretical basis of creativity, anyone can produce the ability of innovation, no matter what the industry he is engaged in and what the nature is, as long as there is an appropriate enterprise environment and enterprise organizational atmosphere, he can be stimulated the potential of his innovation ability. In today's economic globalization, China's textile and garment enterprises need the innovation of all employees in the face of macroeconomic development and huge pressure of survival, especially the innovation behavior of front-line employees. However, the innovation behavior of employees in the company is not as highly alive as it should be in the company. Many employees are afraid of the risks brought by innovation and the influence of other employees' views on it because of innovation. As enterprise leaders, they have not been able to pay attention to the recognition and encouragement of employee innovation behavior under the cultural cultivation. No matter from any angle, the research on employee innovation behavior has been the focus of academic research. Scholars try to open the "black box" that affects employee innovation behavior, explore the path that affects employee innovation behavior, and then achieve the purpose of maximizing utility (Tang 2021). Since the implementation of the "13th Five-Year Plan", China has been actively advancing on the road of building a well-off society in an all-round way to enable the people of the whole country to live a rich life. Facing the improvement of consumers' consumption level of textiles, the domestic

market has produced great pressure on the development of textile industry. In order to meet the needs of the domestic market, China's textile and garment enterprises are continuously improving their competitiveness and market core position. Under the background of market economy, textile and garment enterprises want to maintain their core competitiveness, they must focus on the development of enterprise culture from the source. Culture, as a source to maintain the competitive advantage of textile and garment enterprises, plays a very important role in the innovation of textile and garment enterprises.

Problem Statement

Joseph Alois Schumpeter, an economics professor at Harvard University who is regarded as the ancestor of modern innovation theory, is recognized as the founder of innovation research. As early as the beginning of the 20th century, he creatively put forward the concept of "Innovation", which provided a new theoretical guidance for the production development of enterprises. With China's economic strength becoming stronger and stronger, the party and the state have pushed the implementation of innovation-driven development strategy to an unprecedented height since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, and the intensity is attracting people's attention. On September 30, 2013, Chinese President Xi Jinping pointed out that innovation is the first driving force to lead development, and pointed out that China must use innovation to realize the transformation of development mode as soon as possible, so that the development potential of Chinese society and people can be better released. At the Davos Forum in the summer of 2014, Premier Li Keqiang called out a strong voice of innovation on behalf of the national government. For the first time, he proposed "Business startups and innovation", opening the curtain of the times for this grand event of National innovation. The concept of "dual innovation" has made innovation a household trend of the times. In May 2015, the State Council issued the "Made in China 2025" document, which deployed the strategic arrangement of comprehensively promoting the implementation of a manufacturing power from the macro level. This is an important guarantee measure to vigorously promote the transformation and upgrading of the national economy and domestic industries, and provides strategic guidance for transformation and upgrading and the realization of leapfrog development. It can be seen from this that innovation has been included in the level of national strategy and has become the first element to promote national development and progress.(Cheng 2021; Jia et al. 2020). China not only lacks support and affirmation for individual innovation of employees in material level, but also lacks practice in soft environment construction. With the acceleration of China's participation in global economic activities, China's enterprises are facing increasing external competitive pressure. Enterprises begin to think about how to guide employees' individual innovation behavior and stimulate employees' creative vitality through the construction of enterprise innovation culture, to achieve the goal of improving the level of enterprise innovation and development.

Research Objectives

Based on the research of domestic and foreign related literature, this paper summarizes and analyzes the research and current situation of enterprise cultural characteristics, and adopts the method of combining theory with practice to carry out empirical analysis and research on the influence of enterprise cultural characteristics on employee innovation behavior in textile and garment enterprises in China. The main research purposes are as follows:

- (1) Through the theoretical research and sorting out of enterprise cultural characteristics, the paper summarizes what factors influence corporate cultural characteristics in the specific industry of textile and garment enterprises.
- (2) How does the cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises affect the innovation behavior of employees?

Scope of Study

This paper constructs a model of cultural characteristics specific to the textile and apparel industry through a theoretical review of cultural characteristics, work engagement and employee innovation behavior in textile and garment companies, and investigates its influence on employee innovation behavior. Using work engagement as a mediating variable, the exploratory factor analysis and the validated factor analysis are used to identify the validity of the model of the influence of cultural characteristics on employees' innovation behavior in textile and garment enterprises, and the significant influence of the dimensions of cultural characteristics and work engagement on employees' innovation behavior in textile and garment enterprises is explored in depth. The findings of the study are analyzed to provide a reliable reference value for textile and apparel enterprises to achieve cultural self-improvement and the positive influence effect on employee innovation behavior to maintain their sustainable competitiveness in the market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Innovation Behavior

The word "innovation" originated from the word "Innovare", which means to create new things or to update or change. It first appeared in 1912 in "The Theory of Economic Development", written by the famous economist Joseph A. Schumpeter, who understood innovation to be the creation of a new production function from the point of view of economic output, a reorganization of the factors of production by entrepreneurs. Any change in one of these factors causes a change in the production function, which leads to the development of the economy. The essence of innovation is to innovate its ideas, and innovation is the main source of core competitiveness in an organization. Therefore, innovation can be divided into three different levels, namely, organization, group and individual. The individual's innovation is the most fundamental stone in innovation, which is expressed in the individual's innovative behavior, and this behavior is precisely the process of practicing the new idea of innovation.

Previous Research

Zhao (2021) believes that individual innovation behavior has three dimensions, and has developed the corresponding measurement scale. However, his empirical research results show that individual innovation behavior is a one-dimensional construct. The one-dimensional scale has been widely recognized by researchers, and is the most widely used scale to measure employee innovation behavior in China. Cheng (2021) developed a five-dimensional scale based on reviewing previous research results, which includes finding opportunities, generating ideas, evaluating ideas, supporting innovation, and implementing applications. Tang (2021) refined and partially adjusted Kleysen & Street's five-dimensional measurement scale, and divided its measurement scale into two dimensions, namely, idea generation and idea implementation. Jing (2021) put forward a scale of individual employee innovation behavior in the workplace, which has 13 measurement items.

Figure 2-1 Measurement dimensions of employee innovation behavior

Enterprise culture

The related research on enterprise culture has been in the academic circles for more than 30 years, during which scholars have also published a large number of research works and related academic articles, but there is no unified conclusion on the definition of enterprise culture. The term "enterprise culture" was first seen in the management theory of western enterprises, which believes that corporate management should be based on culture. Enterprise culture is well known from four best-selling books in the 1980s, "Theory Z: How American Business Can Meet the Japanese Challenge", written by William Ouchi; "The Art of Japanese Management", co-authored by Richard T. and Pascale; "Corporate Culture", co-authored by Deal and Kennedy and "In search of excellence - Lessons from America's Best-Run Companies", co-authored by Peters. and Waterman. However, they do not elaborate on the connotation of enterprise culture and make a clear explanation. As for the definition of enterprise culture, scholars at home and abroad mainly explain it from the following angles:

(1) From the perspective of cultural elements: According to Tagiuri and Litwin (1968), "Corporate culture is a feeling or atmosphere that interacts within a company through objects or structures, or the way members interact with each other internally and between members and customers". Peters and Waterman defines corporate culture as "a sense of purpose in which employees make extraordinary contributions and thus also have a high value, which comes from a love of production, products, a desire to improve quality, service and encourage innovation, as well as recognition and honor for each individual's contribution ". The definition given by Pascal (1981) argues that "corporate culture is a belief or purpose that is pursued by all employees within the company and which applies only to the characteristics of the company". William Ouchi (1981) believes that a company's culture contains the patterns that the company uses to define its organizational activities, opinions and behaviors, and also contains its values that are constantly transmitted in the organization, such as the ideologies of aggressiveness and flexibility, which are composed of the practices and ethos of the company. As far as the concept of innovative culture is concerned, it has a long history and is not a new thing, but the research on innovative organizational culture started late, and the division of measurement dimensions is also a hundred schools of thought, and there is no authoritative and unified statement. Compared with foreign studies, Chinese scholars' construction of innovation culture is relatively late, which came into being under the background of " rejuvenating the country through science and education" and developed together in the construction of national innovation system. Different definitions of innovation culture will lead to different measurement methods and results, and there is still no widely recognized measurement scale in management circles. Because different organizations and individuals in different research fields use the word innovation, its conceptual scope is too broad, so that there are relatively few empirical studies on innovation culture. However, from the point of view of quantitative analysis, it is basically the same, and from the point of view of specific index settings, the difference is not very big. Because of Professor Zheng's pioneering research on enterprise culture in Taiwan, China's scholars have also gradually conducted in-depth research on the measurement scale of enterprise culture. Hao et al. (2020) conducted on-the-spot investigation on the middle-level and high-level leaders of 120 state-owned enterprises in relatively developed areas in China, such as Shanghai and other provinces and cities in 2006. The survey results show that there are ten different dimensions of enterprise culture, which are closely related to the internal comprehensiveness and external adaptability of the enterprise, as shown in Figure 2-4.

Figure:2-3 Denison's OCQ scale of enterprise culture

The Chinese entrepreneur survey system divides enterprise culture into five dimensions suitable for Chinese enterprises, namely, employee development and team cooperation, social responsibility, customer orientation, system standardization, innovation and entrepreneurship, and conducts tests on this basis. Song (2020) conducted an exploratory analysis and research on the composition of enterprise culture in China. Through questionnaires and interviews with Chinese companies, he constructed ten cultural measurement dimensions of Chinese corporate culture: ethical and profit orientation, customer and self-orientation, long-term and short-term orientation, innovative and conservative orientation, relationship and work orientation, outcome and process orientation, collective and individual orientation, employee growth and instrumental orientation, open and closed orientation of communication, and institutional and personal authority orientation.

Internal integration	
1 Contribution; (1) Innovative spirit and hard work (2) Dedication (3) Loyalty to organization (4) Professional standards	2 Staff development: (1) Tapping the potential of employees (2) Employee Involvement (3) Balance between employee spirit and centralized decision-making (4) Employee benefits organization (5) Personality development of employees (6) Balance between institutional control and self-restraint (7) Ideological discipline
3 Loyalty to organization (4) Professional standards	4 Leadership; (1) Set an example (2) Personal tasks for employees leadership (3) Ethical action (4) Leadership and responsibilities (5) Skills and technology development
5 Pragmatism; (1) Set clear goals and evaluation (2) Coherence and unified (3) Clear job expectations and responsibilities (4) Comprehensive and complete system development	6 Rewards; (1) Fair remuneration and balance (2) Fairness and punishment (3) Reward and according to work results
External adaptation	
1 Customer Orientation: The organization provides services to customers to make them satisfied (1) First-class service (2) Sincere and reliable service (3) Customers come first (4) Focus on total quality management	2 Future orientation: The organization emphasizes future development and has specific policies and rules to ensure high-level performance (1) Clear goals and tasks (2) Balance between long-term mode benefits and short-term benefits (3) Standards of excellence
3 Innovation: The organization spares no effort in product innovation and organizational interests (1) Innovation (2) Reform-oriented thinking (3) Performance and results of the unit (4) Social responsibility	4 Results-oriented: (1) Balance between corporate interests and social interests (2) Revitalization of national enterprises (3) Performance and results of the unit (4) Social responsibility

Figure:2-4 Cultural measurement scale of domestic state-owned enterprises

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In order to better and more accurately identify and measure the corporate cultural characteristics of textile and apparel companies, this study follows Denison's corporate cultural characteristics measurement scale and makes some improvements to the corporate cultural characteristics applicable to the Chinese context, with the aim of constructing a scale applicable to the cultural characteristics of textile and apparel companies. Denison's OCQ measurement scale of enterprise cultural characteristics contains four dimensions: involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission.

Population / Sampling / Unit of Analysis

In the past, the research on enterprise cultural characteristics often did not focus on a specific industry, but in various industries to investigate enterprise cultural characteristics, and on this basis to draw conclusions. Therefore, the lack of professional pertinence makes the research results can not be well applied in a certain industry field, resulting in the slow development of textile and garment industry in the background of economic globalization, especially China's textile industry, is still in a backward position in the world. This paper conducts field research on textile and garment enterprises in Zhejiang Province. In this paper, 600 questionnaires were distributed to textile and garment enterprises in Zhejiang Province, 568 questionnaires were collected, 550 questionnaires were valid, and the effective completion rate was 91.67%. Distribution and collection time of questionnaires: First of all, to conduct pre-test analysis. The pre-test questionnaire was distributed during June 2021. On the basis of pre-test, the formal questionnaire was distributed and collected from July 2021 to November 2021. To ensure the voluntariness of the questionnaire, this questionnaire was designed to support respondents to voluntarily leave their contact information via email so that they can continue to be informed of the results of this study subsequently. This means that the bias caused by the respondents' unwillingness to fill in the questionnaire has been well controlled in the process of research design, thus ensuring the voluntariness of the questionnaire.

Instrumentation

Measurement scale of cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises

In this paper, Denison's OCQ corporate culture scale was selected as the basis and a measurement scale applicable to the cultural characteristics of textile and apparel companies according to the Chinese context was designed. This is because Denison's corporate cultural characteristics scale has been continuously improved in the course of Denison's and later people' research, and has relative stability and reliability through many empirical studies and revisions. After confirming the scale model of enterprise culture measurement, this paper uses interview and qualitative research methods to make preliminary selection for each dimension of textile and garment enterprise cultural characteristic evaluation, as shown in Table 3-1:

Table 3-1 Composition of dimensions of enterprise culture measurement scale

Measurement scale for cultural characteristics of textile and garment companies	
Involvement	Empowerment Teamwork Valuing Talent
Consistency	Core Values Scientific Management Cultural Identity
Mission	Strategic Orientation Social Responsibility Vision and Goals
Adaptability	Innovation and Transformation Customer Orientation Corporate Governance
Open-ended question: In addition to the four dimensions of involvement, consistency, mission, and adaptability proposed in this questionnaire regarding cultural characteristics, what other dimensions of textile and garment cultural characteristics do you think should be examined?	
What are your recommendations:	

After the expert interviews, the measurement scale was scored and suggestions were made based on the experts' understanding of the cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises, and then combined with relevant theoretical information, the data from the interviews were organized and standardized, adjustments were made, and the measurement scale of the cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises was initially constructed, including four dimensions of involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission. The scale consists of 23 questions, including 6 questions on involvement, 6 questions on consistency, 5 questions on mission, and 6 questions on adaptability. The measurement scale uses 7-point Likert scale, as shown in Table 3-2:

Table 3-2 Measurement scale of cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises

Variables	Sub-dimensions	Test Items
cultural characteristics of textile and garment companies (A)	Consistency (a1)	a11 The core of the corporate culture of your enterprise enables you to have consistent values, and its values act on the cohesion function and guiding function of your enterprise.
		a12 Do you think that your company's culture can coordinate the various elements of its internal capabilities and contribute to the enhancement and expansion of the capabilities of company?
		a13 Your company is able to promote employee unity.
		a14 Your company's culture can effectively influence its ability to adapt to the external and internal environment, and can be subject to change and regulation.
Involvement (a2)		a15 The internal atmosphere of your company is more harmonious.
		a16 Your organization has a clear culture and values that influence and govern the way members behave.
		a21 Your company's employees are able to cooperate extensively with each other.
		a22 You are able to follow the values of your company and are able to generate positive and proactive abilities in your work and work wholeheartedly for the company.
		a23 Your employees can be given certain authority to work independently.
		a24 Innovative employees in your company will be valued.
Adaptability (a3)		a25 Your company organizes staff training every year to improve their work skills.
		a26 Your company is able to give extra attention to innovative and outstanding talents.
		a31 Your company usually learns and adopts some new and improved ways of working.
		a32 Your company focuses on the continuous innovation of product technology.
		a33 Your company's management style is in line with the humanization requirements.
		a34 Your company is customer service oriented.
Mission (a4)		a35 Your company is the best company in the eyes of your customers.
		a36 Your company promotes learning for the purpose of mutual progress.
		a41 Do you think that your company is very much involved in social affairs and social responsibility?
		a42 You are guided by your company's shared values and are able to maintain alignment with corporate goals and actions.
		a43 The leaders of your company have a long-term vision.
		a44 Your company's culture is unique to your company and creates a competitive advantage for your company.
		a45 Your company has a clear mission and vision for growth.

Reliability Analysis

On the whole, the alpha coefficient is $0.909 > 0.7$, which represents that the overall reliability of the questionnaire is high. See Table 3-8 for details:

Table 3-8 Reliability analysis of the overall measurement scale

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items	Number of items
0.910	0.909	54

Validity Analysis

The so-called validity refers to the degree to which the psychological or behavioral characteristics predicted by the test can be measured. The validity of research includes intrinsic validity and external validity. Intrinsic validity refers to the correctness and authenticity of research, while external validity refers to the correctness of research inference. Factor analysis is the most commonly used method to test construct validity in statistics. If the user uses factor analysis to test the validity of the test tool and effectively extracts common factors, which are very close to the psychological characteristics of the theoretical framework, the test tool or scale can be said to have construct validity.

(1) Validity analysis of cultural characteristic measurement scale: In this paper, factor analysis is mainly used to test the validity, and the principal component analysis method of factor analysis is adopted. In the selection of the number of factors, according to Kaise, the factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 are reserved as the selection criteria. In accordance with the above principles and gradual screening, this paper first conducted KMO test and Bartlett's test of sphericity on the cultural characteristic measurement scale, and the results are shown in Table 3-9 below:

Table 3-9 KMO and Bartlett's test of exploratory factor analysis of enterprise cultural characteristics

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy	Metrics	0.866
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1472.926
	df	120
	Sig.	0.000

KMO value is in the range of 0 to 1, when KMO value is less than 0.50, it is not suitable to carry out factor analysis; When the KMO value is greater than 0.80, it indicates that the relationship between variables is good and suitable for factor analysis. When the KMO value is greater than 0.90, it indicates that the relationship between various variables is optimal, which is very suitable for factor analysis.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of Respondents: Sample distribution

The statistical data in this paper are processed by SPSS 22.0, Amos5.0 and other statistical software. The questionnaire distribution involves four representative textile and garment enterprises, and a total of 560 valid samples are collected. This paper is mainly aimed at the textile and garment industry, so the selection of samples has a strong representativeness. The first part of the questionnaire is the basic information of the investigated object, covering the basic information of the respondents, such as gender, age, working years, education background, etc. The data analysis results are shown in the sample distribution overview table for details:

(1) Gender distribution of respondents

Figure 4-1 Pie chart of gender distribution of respondents

As can be seen from Fig. 4-1, the gender distribution of the respondents is:

(2) Age distribution of respondents

From the age distribution of the respondents, employees under 30 years old accounted for 48.7% of the total number of employees, employees between 30 and 40 years old accounted for 28.6% of the total number of employees, employees between 40 and 50 years old accounted for 15.3% of the total number of employees, and employees over 50 years old accounted for 7.4% of the total number of employees, as shown in Table 4-1. It can be seen that the overall staff of textile and garment enterprises is inclined to be younger. With the development of the times, the young and middle-aged employees in textile and garment enterprises will become the core strength of the enterprises to maintain the level of competitiveness, and the age distribution of the respondents is relatively reasonable for the age distribution of this survey respondents.

Table 4-1 Age distribution of respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Effective percentage	Cumulative percentage
Under 30 years old	99	48.7	48.7	48.7
30-40 years old	58	28.6	28.6	77.3
40 - 50 years old	31	15.3	15.3	92.6
Over 50 years old	15	7.4	7.4	100.0

(3) Educational background distribution of respondents

Figure 4-2 Column diagram of education background distribution of respondents

Statistical description of enterprise culture measurement scale

As shown in Table 4-3, the mean value of mission of cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises is at the highest level in cultural characteristics, and the mean value of consistency is at the lowest level in cultural characteristics.

Table 4-3 Descriptive statistics of cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises

Variables	N	Minimal value	Maximum value	Mean Value	Standard deviation	Variance
Involvement	203	1.00	5.00	3.6404	.78586	.618
Consistency	203	1.00	5.00	3.3350	.89890	.808
Mission	203	2.00	5.00	3.7783	.68587	.470
Adaptability	203	2.00	5.00	3.6749	.66206	.438

Statistical description of work engagement measurement scale

Table 4-4 Descriptive statistics of work engagement

Variables	N	Minimal value	Maximum value	Mean Value	Standard deviation	Variance
Absorption	203	1.00	5.00	3.2660	.69687	.879
Dedication	203	1.00	5.00	4.2956	.67577	.360
Vigor	203	1.00	5.00	4.8325	.48336	.301

As can be seen from Table 4-4, the overall work engagement is at a medium-to-high level, with the highest mean value of vigor and the lowest mean value of absorption, but the difference between the three is not large.

Statistical description of employee innovation behavior measurement scale

Table 4-5 Descriptive statistics of employee innovation behavior

Variables	N	Minimal value	Maximum value	Mean Value	Standard deviation	Variance
Innovative behavior generation	203	1.00	5.00	4.3990	.56442	.665
Innovative behavior implementation	203	1.00	5.00	4.0394	.58053	.820
Innovative behavior	203	1.00	4.75	4.4384	.51905	.681

As can be seen from Table 4-5, the two dimensions of employee innovation behavior generation and employee innovation behavior implementation both reach a high level, wherein the mean value of innovation behavior generation is greater than that of innovation behavior implementation, and the employee innovation behavior is generally at a high level.

Results

(1) Correlation analysis between textile and garment enterprise cultural characteristics and employee innovation behavior

Table 4-8 Correlation between each dimension of cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises and employee innovation behavior

Variables	Relevance	Involvement	Consistency	Mission	Adaptability	Innovative behavior
Involvement	Pearson correlation	1	.699**	.722**	.717**	.587**
	Significance (two-sided)		.000	.000	.000	.000
Consistency	Pearson correlation	.699**	1	.676**	.634**	.428**
	Significance (two-sided)	.000		.000	.000	.000
Mission	Pearson correlation	.722**	.676**	1	.674**	.504**
	Significance (two-sided)	.000	.000		.000	.000
Adaptability	Pearson correlation	.717**	.634**	.674**	1	.543**
	Significance (two-sided)	.000	.000	.000		.000
Innovative behavior	Pearson correlation	.587**	.428**	.504**	.543**	1
	Significance (two-sided)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

Note a: **. represents a significant correlation at the 0.01 level (two-sided).

From Table 4-8, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient between employee innovation behavior and the involvement dimension of textile and garment enterprise cultural characteristics is 0.587, the correlation coefficient between employee innovation behavior and the consistency dimension is 0.428, the correlation coefficient between employee innovation

behavior and the mission dimension is 0.504, and the correlation coefficient between employee innovation behavior and the adaptability dimension is 0.543. Among them, the level of significance test of correlation coefficients between each dimension of textile and garment enterprise cultural characteristics and employee innovation behavior is 0, which shows that there is a linear relationship between them.

(2) Regression analysis of cultural characteristics of textile and garment enterprises and employee innovation behavior: From Tables 4-9, it can be seen that consistency, involvement, mission, and adaptability significantly influence employee innovative behavior ($p < 0.01$, $\beta = -0.020$; $p < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.154$; $p < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.042$; $p < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.070$), which verifies Hypothesis H1 and indicates that the textile and garment corporate cultural characteristics significantly influence employee innovative behavior, with participation, mission, and adaptability having a significant positive effect and consistency having a significant negative effect.

Table 4-9 Regression analysis of each dimension of textile and garment enterprise cultural characteristics and employee innovation behavior

Variables	Employee Innovation Behavior	
	Model 1	Model 2
Gender	-0.061	-0.051
Age	0.159	0.143
Educational background	0.116	0.038
Position	0.041	0.017
Years of work	-0.100	-0.074
Consistency		-0.020**
Involvement		0.154**
Mission		0.042**
Adaptability		0.070**
R ²	0.029	0.410
Sig. R ²	0.004	0.382
F-value	1.175	14.887

The effects of corporate cultural characteristics on employee innovative behavior are concluded as follows: involvement, mission, and adaptability had a significant positive impact on employee innovative behavior ($p < 0.01$, $\beta = -0.020$; $p < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.154$; $p < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.042$; $p < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.070$), while consistency had a significant negative impact on employee innovation behavior ($p < 0.01$, $\beta = -0.020$). Hypotheses H1a, H1b, H1c and H1d are all valid, and Hypothesis H1 is also valid.

Discussion

Empirical studies of organizational culture factors as main effects mostly use the corporate culture as a whole or a particular aspect as the independent variable to study the impact on employee innovative behavior. Enterprise culture interacts and promotes with employee behavior. Enterprise culture affects employee behavior as a common value, and employee behavior habits gradually form enterprise culture (Cheng 2021). The individual behavior of employee is affected by the interaction between individual and environment (Liu et al. 2021). When individual and environment maintain consistency and coordination, their innovation behavior will increase significantly (Tang 2021). The social exchange theory holds that all individual behaviors are exchange activities based on economic remuneration. In order to meet their own survival needs, employees exchange compensation rewards from the organization through their efforts, and when the fairer material exchange, employees will show more positive behaviors. At the same time, when employees get positive rewards for positive behavior, it will in turn stimulate them to try to perform more innovation behavior at work, however, it is not the case that the higher the salary incentive is, the better the reinforcement effect of individual positive behaviors is (Cheng 2021; Jia et al. 2020). The cultural elements of

promoting innovation in an organization are mainly reflected in encouraging, supporting and recognizing employee innovation behavior, creating a learning atmosphere, making flexible and rapid decision-making, taking the market as the center to meet customer needs, and flexible and environment-friendly organizational structure (Tang 2021; Xu et al. 2020). By creating a good innovation atmosphere, individual members within the organization can perceive the enterprise's demand, attitude and support for innovation. Enterprise innovation culture encourages employees to sprout creative new ideas in their work, stimulates individual innovation vigor, and plays a great role in promoting employee innovation behavior. The norms of organizational environment and code of conduct affect the individual behavior of employees in enterprises, and through appropriate guidance, employees can make the behavior beneficial to the organization that the enterprise hopes. At present, some empirical research results confirm that innovation culture, group culture and learning culture all have positive effects on individual innovation behavior.

CONCLUSION

To adhere to the cultivation of enterprise innovation culture. This study shows that corporate innovation culture has a significant positive impact on employee innovation behavior. Enterprise innovation culture plays an obvious role in promoting employee innovation behavior and building enterprise core competitiveness. First, enterprise leaders should attach great importance to it (Cheng 2021). Cultural factors can not be completed in a short time. If there is no strong support from the leadership level, cultural construction will inevitably have little effect. Second, the construction of enterprise innovation culture should be maintained consistently in the process of practice, otherwise it will frustrate the enthusiasm of employees and thus affect individual innovation behavior. For example, after a company proposes an innovative work goal, employees actively participate and invest a lot of time and energy, but the company end up with nothing definite; or even if the innovation fails, the company makes employees take responsibility independently, which will affect the construction of corporate innovation culture. Third, give knowledge-based workers more independent work space. Through participating in management, work involvement and other ways, let the employees of the enterprise participate in various activities of the enterprise more widely, moderately authorize the employees to do their work more autonomous, give employees more power of discourse, and improve the enthusiasm and initiative of the employees in innovation. Fourth, enterprises should advocate team spirit. Although innovation depends on individual innovation behavior, it is difficult for one person's innovation to effectively support the enterprise to survive and develop in the fierce market competition. Therefore, it is necessary to encourage team cooperation, establish and improve the cooperation mechanism, unblock horizontal communication channels, and let the spirit of team cooperation be implemented in every activity of the enterprise (Liu et al. 2021). To guide employees to establish innovative work values. From the results of this study, the work values variable and its two sub-dimensions have a significant positive impact on employee innovation behavior variables. As a mediating variable, corporate innovation culture affects employee work values, and then affects employee innovation behavior. Therefore, enterprises should guide employees to actively establish innovative values. First, help employees grow and recognize self-worth and the meaning of their work. Enterprises should enable employees to understand themselves and the company more clearly, and fully realize the work value of their posts. Only by identifying with the enterprise can they more actively help the development of the enterprise and stimulate more potential. Second, enterprises should help employees formulate career plans in combination with their actual situation. Based on the above analysis of the differences in demographic variables, it can be known that employees of different gender, age and education levels have different values (Tang 2021). Effective implementation of career management and

continuous training opportunities for employees to grow in their jobs will enable them to be more creative and generate more innovative behaviors. Third, be good at inspiring and encouraging employees to innovate through their work value preferences. According to the empirical results of this study, people of different genders, ages and educational backgrounds have different priorities in terms of work values, and companies need to implement guidance and motivation in a more localized manner. For example, for college students just out of college, they are more concerned about the accumulation of knowledge and work experience, and the importance of short-term benefits in material aspects is relatively weaker. Enterprises can strengthen vocational training to quickly improve their working ability, so that they gradually have the basic quality of innovation (Jing 2021).

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